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WP3 – Personalized Medicine

D3.8 Final Report on the implementation of the analytical pipeline for personalized medicine

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DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Description
V0.1	2022-10-28	Internal Review
V1.1	2022-11-07	Revised version for consortium review
V1.1final	2022-11-17	Final version for submission

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	Forum Europeen des Patients (FPE) - Belgium
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene / BMS	Celgene Management SARL – Switzerland
BI	Boehringer Ingelheim International GmbH – Germany
HLU	H. Lundbeck AS - Denmark

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The goal of WP3 “Personalized Medicine” is to establish a standardized process to enable personalized decision-making that can be utilized for multiple outcomes of interest and can be applied to observational healthcare data from any patient subpopulation.

In the first report (D3.2) on the implementation of the analytical pipeline for personalized medicine, we introduced the analytical pipelines for Patient-Level Prediction and Population-Level Effect Estimation. Furthermore, we discussed our initial work for the development of a pipeline for Risk Stratified Effect Estimation to assess heterogeneity of treatment effect.

In the second report (D3.4) we provided an update on the work done in the second year, including heterogeneity of treatment effect (HTE), and disease trajectory analyses. That deliverable included an overview of use cases in which the analytical pipelines have been applied and described the advances made in methodological research, the start of a natural language processing pipeline, and work done to develop a pipeline for disease trajectories.

In the third report (D3.6) we provided further updates to the methodological research and the introduction of new tools including exhaustive search and frequent pattern mining, the use of unstructured data in predictive analytics as well as publishing a systematic review on clinical prediction modelling.

In this final report (D3.8) we introduce new additional analytical tools and provide a further update on the methodological research and clinical applications.

This work falls under Task 3.2. “Development of an integrated patient-level prediction pipeline” (M6-M60), Task 3.3 “Development of an integrated risk-effect estimation pipeline” (M6-M60), and Task 3.4 “Development of a pipeline for disease trajectory analysis” (M12-M36).

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1. INTRODUCTION

The goal of WP3 is to build analytical pipelines that can utilize all the data in the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM) for patient-level prediction (PLP), population-level effect estimation (PLE), heterogeneity of treatment effect (HTE), and disease trajectory analyses. By conducting research on these topics, we aim to further help in treatment personalization. In this short deliverable we provide an update on the analytical pipeline development and methodological research.

In this reporting period many additional agile development steps have been made on the R packages that have been described in more detail in previous deliverables (see Table 1). This includes the addition of functionality, documentation updates, code restructuring, etc. The packages are currently hosted on GitHub within EHDEN, OHDSI, and the Erasmus MC GitHub organization but these will in the near future be located in the OHDSI repository. We refer to these repositories for more details on the release updates etc. For example, in the PatientLevelPrediction R package functionality was added to perform recalibration of predictive models as discussed as next step in deliverable D3.4 and logged in the [package news](#).

Table 1. Overview of R packages

Package	Description
OHDSI/PatientLevelPrediction	An R package for performing patient level prediction in an observational database in the OMOP CDM .
OHDSI/CohortMethod	An R package for performing new-user cohort studies in an observational database in the OMOP CDM.
OHDSI/RiskStratifiedEstimation	An R package for performing effect estimation in risk strata to assess treatment effect heterogeneity
EHDEN/Trajectories	An R package for detecting and visualizing statistically significant event sequences in OMOP CDM data.
mi-erasmusmc/Triton	An R package for creating covariates from unstructured text in OMOP CDM data.
mi-erasmusmc/Explore	An R package for finding a short and accurate decision rule in disjunctive normal form by exhaustive search
mi-erasmusmc/AssociationRuleMining	An R package that implements association rule mining and frequent pattern mining against the OMOP-CDM
OHDSI/DeepPatientLevelPrediction	An R package for performing patient level prediction using deep learning models in an observational database in the OMOP CDM.

Table 1 contains three new analytical tools, which we will describe in the methods research section below: one for searching exhaustively for optimal decision rules, one for performing association-rule mining and frequent-pattern analysis and one for using deep learning models to do patient level prediction.

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For most of our work articles have already been submitted to peer-reviewed journals and made available as preprint for community feedback. Where applicable we have added links to these preprints, and other material such as posters, videos, and demos.

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2. METHODS RESEARCH

2.1 Predictive analytics using unstructured data

We developed TRITON as standardized NLP pipeline tool, within the OHDSI framework, for extracting textual features in a data-driven and language-independent manner. This tool extends the FeatureExtraction framework in the form of a custom covariate builder and constructs a set of text-based covariates based on the CDM *note* table. Text Represented In Terms Of Numeric-features (TRITON) is publicly available on GitHub at github.com/mi-erasmusmc/Triton.

Additional to the ability to create sparse bag-of-word text representations, it is also possible to use and create dense text representations such as topic models and word or document embeddings. Furthermore, TRITON has the ability of creating features based on information in the DCM *note_nlp* table. This *note_nlp* table has to be populated first with clinical concepts extracted from the text and can include contextual information (e.g., negation, experiencer, and temporality). We modified the publicly available MedSpacy python library [1] to perform concept extraction from Dutch clinical text.

Our aim is to determine the added value of textual data in electronic health records (EHR) for improving patient-level prediction models. This is currently done in two ways. First, we performed a systematic review on the use of unstructured text data in clinical prognostic prediction models, to summarize the prediction problems and methodological landscape [2]. We discovered that the use of unstructured text in the development of prognostic prediction models has been found beneficial in addition to structured data in most studies. Second, we are investigating a variety of methods to generate features from Dutch clinical text and determine whether predictive performance improves if these features are used on their own and in addition to the features based on structured data. Different feature sets, including bag-of-words, topic-models, averaged textual embeddings, and extracted clinical concepts, will be generated using the TRITON framework and tested for their predictive value using various prediction problems. The development of this tool should add another potential avenue for treatment personalisation by allowing for the free text information to be used for prediction modelling.

References

- [1] Eyre, H., et al., Launching into clinical space with medspaCy: a new clinical text processing toolkit in Python. arXiv preprint arXiv:2106.07799, 2021.
- [2] Seinen, T., et al.. Use of unstructured text in prognostic clinical prediction models: a systematic review. Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association 29.7 (2022): 1292-1302.

2.2 Class imbalance methods

In our previous systematic review on clinical prediction modeling using EHR data, we found that class imbalance methods were increasingly applied in the period 2009-2019 (1). However, there is currently no consensus on the impact of class imbalance methods on the performance of clinical prediction models. We aimed to empirically investigate the impact of random oversampling and random undersampling, two commonly used class imbalance methods, on the internal and external validation performance of prediction models developed using observational health data.

We developed and externally validated prediction models for various outcomes of interest within a target population of people with pharmaceutically treated depression across four observational health databases. We used three different classifiers (lasso logistic regression, random forest, XGBoost) and varied the target imbalance ratio. We evaluated the impact on model performance in terms of discrimination and calibration.

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Discrimination was assessed using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC) and calibration was assessed using calibration plots.

We developed and externally validated a total of 1,566 prediction models. On internal validation, random oversampling and random undersampling on average did not improve the AUROC. Both random oversampling and random undersampling resulted in overestimated risks, although we found that this miscalibration could largely be corrected by recalibrating the models towards the original imbalance ratios. On external validation, random sampling also did not improve model performance.

Our results suggest that random oversampling and random undersampling on average do not improve the internal and external validation performance of prediction models in terms of discrimination and calibration. Based on our findings, we do not recommend applying random oversampling or random undersampling when developing prediction models using large observational health data.

The paper is currently under peer review at a journal.

References

[1] Yang C, Kors JA, Ioannou S, John LH, Markus AF, Rekkas A, et al. Trends in the conduct and reporting of clinical prediction model development and validation: a systematic review. *J Am Med Inform Assoc.* 2022.

2.3 External validation of existing dementia prediction models

Many dementia prediction models have been developed, but only few have been externally validated, which hinders clinical uptake and may pose a risk if models are applied to actual patients regardless. Externally validating a prediction model is a difficult task, where we mostly rely on the completeness of model reporting in a published article.

In this study, we aim to externally validate existing dementia prediction models. To that end, we define model reporting criteria, review published studies, and externally validate three well reported models using routinely collected health data from administrative claims and electronic health records.

We identified dementia prediction models that were developed between 2011 – 2020 and assessed if they could be externally validated given a set of model criteria. In addition, we externally validated three of these models (Walters’ Dementia Risk Score, Mehta’s RxDx-Dementia Risk Index, and Nori’s ADRD dementia prediction model) on a network of six observational health databases from the United States, United Kingdom, Germany and the Netherlands, including the original development databases of the models. More details about the development databases can be found in Table 2.

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Table 2. Data sources selected for external validation of selected dementia prediction models.

Database	Acronym	No. of patients (million)	Country	Data type
IBM MarketScan® Medicare Supplemental Database	MDCR	10	United States	Claims
Iqvia Germany DA	IQGER	30	Germany	GP, EHR
Optum's de-identified Clinformatics® Data Mart Database	OPSES	85	United States	Claims
Optum® de-identified Electronic Health Record dataset	OPEHR	94	United States	EHR
Clinical Practice Research Datalink	CPRD	13	United Kingdom	GP
Integrated Primary Care Information	IPCI	2.5	Netherlands	GP
Iqvia Medical Research Database (incorporating THIN)	IMRD	18	United Kingdom	GP

We reviewed 59 dementia prediction models for validation criteria, which can be found in Table 3.

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Table 3. Model validation criteria that prediction studies should report to enable external validation.

Category	Validation criteria	Description
Population settings	Target population definition	Definition or description of the population for which predictions are made.
	Index date	Date at which a patient qualifies for inclusion in the target population.
	Time-at-risk	Time window in which a model's predictions are valid relative to the index date.
	Outcome definition	Definition or description of the outcome to be predicted during the time-at-risk.
Statistical analysis settings	Prediction method	Prediction methods in this study are limited to logistic regression and Cox proportional hazard for predicting a binary outcome.
	Predictor definitions	Predictor descriptions or definitions in terms of data source codes.
	Predictor time window	Time window in which the predictor is assessed. In a special case, a predictor can be assessed in a time window all time prior to index, often reported as "a history of ..." using all available prior data of a person.
	Model specifications	<p>The prediction model, e.g., parameters to construct the model given a prediction method. Alternatively, a risk calculator or nomogram could be reported.</p> <p>We also distinguish here between fully and partially specified models. For example, if no intercept is reported in the case of a logistic regression model, we are still able to construct a simple risk stratification model using only coefficient values. However, this method does not consider the baseline risk of the original model and (re-)calibration will not be assessed.</p>

Table 4 summarizes the result of our literature review with validation criteria reported by each study and model.

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Table 4. Summary of validated prediction models.

Category	Validation criteria	No. of models (%)
Population settings	Target population definition	59 (100)
	Index date	22 (37)
	Time-at-risk	42 (71)
	Outcome definition	59 (100)
Statistical analysis settings	Prediction method	59 (100)
	Predictor definitions	52 (88)
	Predictor time window	21 (36)
	Model specifications: Full model	9 (15)
	Model specifications: Partial model	17 (29)

All models reported the prediction method, development database, and target and outcome definitions. Less frequently reported by these 59 prediction models were predictor definitions (52 models) including the time window in which a predictor is assessed (21 models), predictor coefficients (20 models), and the time-at-risk (42 models). The validated model by Walters (development c-statistic: 0.84) showed moderate transportability (0.67 – 0.76 c-statistic). The Mehta model (development c-statistic: 0.81) transported well to some of the external databases (0.69 – 0.79 c-statistic). The Nori model (development AUROC: 0.69) transported well (0.62 – 0.68 AUROC) but performed modestly overall. Recalibration showed improvements for the Walters and Nori models, while recalibration could not be assessed for the Mehta model due to unreported baseline hazard.

The lack of external validation in dementia prediction literature can to some extent be attributed to the insufficient reporting of models. Models should be developed with external validation in mind. This could for example mean to report all aspects of the model explicitly. Such transparency is best achieved programmatically through code lists and underlying logic rather than literal descriptions, for example by providing a full description of the model (development) in code, ideally against a common data model. This approach will likely eliminate ambiguity as a source of error.

In general, authors should avoid uncommon predictors during model development if the model is meant to be applied in external healthcare settings. Instead of building a single model with multiple, complex cohort entry events, it can be beneficial to build a model for each entry event, which may be easier to interpret and validate. The Nori model suffered from this problem as it had a complex target population definition with multiple entry events. Defining the time-at-risk window is crucial to indicate in which time window a model's predictions are valid. Using the full follow-up of a population is not a valid approach, as follow-up can vary per person.

2.4 Attention-based neural networks for clinical prediction modelling

In this study we develop state-of-the-art deep learning methods using attention and compare their performance with simpler algorithms on data mapped to the OMOP-CDM.

We implement four state-of-the-art approaches along with a linear model on data from a general practitioners database in the Netherlands. We implement a recurrent neural network, a transformer with and without reverse distillation and a graph neural network. All the architectures use attention. We measure discrimination performance using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) and the

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area under the precision recall curve (AUPRC). We assess smooth calibration using restricted cubic splines and clinical utility with decision curve analysis.

Our results show that for some prediction problems the deep learning approaches can improve discrimination up to 2.5 percentage points AUC and 7.4 percentage points AUPRC. However, on average the linear baseline is still competitive. Using reverse distillation to learn first from a linear baseline always improves a normal transformer. Most of the models are similarly calibrated as the linear baseline except for the graph neural network. The transformer using reverse distillation shows the best performance in clinical utility on two out of three prediction problems over most of the prediction thresholds.

There is value in using deep learning models on electronic health record data since it can improve discrimination and clinical utility while providing similar calibration as a linear model. These improvements should lead to better prediction models for personalised medicine.

The paper is currently in submission.

2.5 Deep learning framework

By standardizing the steps of model development based on the common data model, it is possible to ensure model transparency (full development code and the model itself can be shared), simplify external validation and introduce the model to other environments. Reps et al. developed a standardized framework for developing and validating predictive models using well known machine learning algorithms (1). However, deep learning (DL) algorithms have not been fully implemented in existing frameworks.

In this study, we to develop a new framework for developing deep learning models based on the OMOP-CDM.

We developed a new framework to develop DL models based on Torch for (2). This framework has a dependency on the existing OHDSI PatientLevelPrediction package. Any deep learning algorithm topology can be introduced into the package, making it very flexible without dependency on python. Preliminarily, we included several DL algorithms (e.g., simple multilayer perceptron, ResNet, a Transformer etc.) to this package as preset topologies. This package is available as open source (<https://github.com/OHDSI/DeepPatientLevelPrediction>).

For a pilot study to demonstrate this package, we developed and evaluated prediction models on a specific clinical question: “Which patients will develop dementia within 5 years following a GP visit?”.

Study population was elderly patients (50-79 years) who visited a GP with a 1-year observation window in the Integrated Primary Care Information (IPCI) database⁶. This is a database, converted to the OMOP-CDM, including approximately 2.5 million patients from a set of general practitioners (GPs) in the Netherlands. The study was approved by the IPCI review board, registration no. 2/2022. Four algorithms were used: two conventional ML algorithms (Xgboost and lasso logistic regression) and two DL algorithms (Transformer and ResNet from Gorishniy et al) (3). Models were developed using a 25%/75% test/train split with 3-fold cross validation to select optimal hyper-parameters. Model performance was evaluated with the area under the receiver operating characteristics curve (AUC), the area under the precision-recall curve (AUPRC), and Eavg for calibration.

The number of the study population was 301.226, and the rate of dementia within 5 years was 1.6%. Four models were developed using the ML and DL algorithms. The performance result of all models is shown in Table 1. The ResNet and Transformer model had 0.884 and 0.876 of AUC, respectively and those were similar to that of conventional ML models (XGBoost: 0.897; LLR: 0.876). The calibration of the ResNet and

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Transformer was 0.003 and 0.0043 for the Eavg, respectively. All performances of the DL models were comparable that of the conventional ML models, however, they took longer to develop (Table 5).

Table 5. Performance results from the four models developed by different algorithms

	ResNet	Transformer	XGBoost	LLR
AUC	0.884 (0.874-0.893)	0.876 (0.867-0.886)	0.876 (0.867– 0.886)	0.897 (0.886 – 0.903)
AUPRC	0.283	0.282	0.277	0.306
Eavg	3e-3	4.3e-3	8.1e-4	1.3e-3
Time	5.95 hours	2.36 hours*	7.3 min	5.5 min

AUC: area under the receiver operating characteristics curve; AUPRC: area under the precision-recall curve; Eavg: average E value; *One set of hyperparameters

We introduced a new DeepPatientLevelPrediction package to the OHDSI community. By using this package, standardized deep-learning models can be developed based on the OMOP-CDM. Furthermore, it will be utilized for predictive model development using any healthcare data in the OMOP-CDM format.

The package has been released as part of the OHDSI HADES suite of open-source tools.

References

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- [2] Falbel, D., Luraschi, J (2021). torch: Tensors and Neural Networks with 'GPU' Acceleration. R package version 0.6.0. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=torch>
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2.6 Predictive analytics using frequent patterns

Electronic Health Records (EHRs) constitute a rich source of longitudinal information describing patients' encounters with the healthcare system. This longitudinal dimension, usually referred to as temporality, can be described as the timing and spacing of occasions of measurements over a period of time [1]. It can consist of a variety of information including and not limited to diagnoses, symptoms, drug prescription, and laboratory data, as well as unstructured clinical notes and/or radiological images. Temporal information therefore offers a unique opportunity to study the progress of health and disease in patients.

Temporal pattern mining of EHR data has the potential to uncover previously unknown relationships among comorbidities (conditions occurring together and in a temporal order) and treatment pathways (drugs prescribed in a temporal order), which can complement clinical knowledge and traditional medical research methods[2]. Patient level prediction models that make use of standard machine learning algorithms usually

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do not incorporate any form of temporality: concepts are used as features that contain a single numeric or categorical value [3].

In this work we aimed to assess the predictive value of frequent patterns as potential predictor candidates in clinical prediction models. Specifically, we developed several feature sets containing sets of frequent patterns extracted from EHR databases mapped to the OMOP-CDM using the AssociationRuleMining package. We evaluate the method in a cohort of pharmaceutically treated patients for depression - our index date - where we look for the development of 21 outcomes within 180 days. For the baseline problems, we used the presence or not of any previous condition in patients' records as candidate predictors to develop L1 regularised regression models in three US claims databases. For the comparator models, we extract frequent patterns from the patients' 365 days history prior to the index, to include as candidate predictors. We experimented with alternating minimum support and frequent pattern length to examine the impact on predictive performance. Overall, we examine 1008 models comparing their discrimination and calibration.

Overall, baseline models show a moderate to adequate c-statistic (0.63-0.88 CCAE, 0.60-0.90 MDCD, 0.59-0.78 MDCR). Models that incorporate frequent patterns show minimal or no added predictive performance (0.63 – 0.88 CCAE, 0.60 – 0.90 MDCD, 0.57 – 0.78 MDCR). This information is presented in Figure 1. Out of all models, discrimination was improved above 1% (1.3-3.4%) for four of the outcomes. There does not appear to exist any robust improvement across databases. Calibration of the plots was unstable.

Visualising AUC improvement of comparator models to baseline models.

Figure 1: Comparing most predictive comparator models with baseline. Colors denote three databases.

- [1] Timmons, A.C. and K.J. Preacher, *The Importance of Temporal Design: How Do Measurement Intervals Affect the Accuracy and Efficiency of Parameter Estimates in Longitudinal Research?* *Multivariate Behav Res*, 2015. **50**(1): p. 41-55.
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2.7 Risk-based evaluation of treatment effect heterogeneity

Treatment effects can often vary substantially across individual patients, causing overall effect estimates to be inaccurate for a significant proportion of the patients at hand. Understanding heterogeneity of treatment effects (HTE) has been crucial for both personalized (or precision) medicine and comparative effectiveness research, giving rise to a wide range of approaches for its discovery, evaluation and application in clinical practice. Baseline risk is a summary score inherently related to treatment effect that can represent more

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closely the variability in patient characteristics. In the past we proposed a standardized framework for the assessment of treatment effect heterogeneity in the observational setting and developed an open-source R-package for implementing it [1].

We used our approach in the field of osteoporosis comparing teriparatide to oral bisphosphonates. Our primary effectiveness outcome was hip fracture, as this is typically the fracture outcome more reliably recorded in the proposed datasets. Vertebral fracture and a composite major osteoporotic fracture, defined as hip, vertebral or wrist/forearm/proximal humerus fracture, were our secondary effectiveness outcomes. Patient time-at-risk started 1 day after treatment initiation and finished 365 days after treatment initiation. Continuous exposure to the treatments under study was achieved by imposing a maximum of 30 days between prescriptions. In cases where this was not the case, patients were censored upon treatment discontinuation. We also censored patient follow-up in cases of drop out from the database, death or at the time when anti-osteoporotic treatment was switched. We used data from multiple databases mapped to OMOP-CDM to run our analyses. We evaluated both overall and risk-stratified treatment effects, both on the relative and the absolute scale. Our primary results showed a tendency towards favoring teriparatide in patients with low anticipated hip fracture risk. However, there was strong evidence towards unresolved confounding and, therefore, results should be interpreted very cautiously. This work was presented as an oral presentation at ICPE-2022 conference.

In order to better individualize treatment effects using a risk-based approach we carried out a large simulation study that evaluated several easily implemented regression-based methods. More specifically, we simulated RCT data using diverse assumptions for the average treatment effect, a baseline prognostic index of risk (PI), the shape of its interaction with treatment (none, linear, quadratic or non-monotonic), and the magnitude of treatment-related harms (none or constant independent of the PI). We predicted absolute benefit using: models with a constant relative treatment effect; stratification in quarters of the PI; models including a linear interaction of treatment with the PI; models including an interaction of treatment with a restricted cubic spline (RCS) transformation of the PI; an adaptive approach using Akaike's Information Criterion. We evaluated predictive performance using root mean squared error and measures of discrimination and calibration for benefit. Results: The linear-interaction model displayed optimal or close-to-optimal performance across many simulation scenarios with moderate sample size (N=4,250; ~785 events). The RCS-model was optimal for strong non-linear deviations from a constant treatment effect, particularly when sample size was larger (N=17,000). The adaptive approach also required larger sample sizes. This work was presented as an oral presentation at the ISCB2022 conference. It is also under consideration at a scientific journal and can be accessed as a preprint [2].

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2.8 Why predicting risk can't identify 'risk factors'

It is a known misunderstanding that prediction models do not generally assess causality (1, 2). However, even with a correct interpretation, the issue with using prediction models for 'risk factor' discovery (i.e. variables associated to the outcome) is that prediction models are often developed with the aim to obtain the highest predictive performance rather than to identify a complete and consistent set of 'risk factors'. In this work, we investigate the stability of prediction models by performing a large-scale experiment developing over 450

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prediction models and investigating model changes across databases (care settings) and phenotype definitions. This illustrates the potential issues with using prediction models for ‘risk factor’ discovery.

We found a higher number of outcome cases generally leads to more variables being selected using LASSO logistic regression). Next, we observed overall model stability is relatively poor, with a maximum value of 0.18 across prediction tasks (maximum stability is 1). The top 10/25 variables, however, were slightly more stable with a maximum value of 0.44. Figure 2 shows that the impact of different target/outcome phenotype definitions was limited when the number of outcome cases is sufficiently high. However, the influence of database choice was substantial, as can be seen from the low overlap across all prediction tasks for models developed on different databases. This means that the top (i.e. most important) 10 variables differed across databases. Finally, Figure 3 shows that the sign of the coefficient can vary greatly even for the top variables. We do not observe clear difference between prediction tasks, but less selected variables seem more likely to flip sign. These results clearly highlight the issue of interpreting the developed prediction models for ‘risk factor’ effect, as the effect often alternates between a positive and negative association.

Figure 2. Boxplots showing the overlap in the top 10 variables as defined by counting the number of common variables between each pair of models for same/different database (D), target population definition (T), outcome definition (O) across models.

Figure 3. Graph visualizing the number of times variables are selected and the percentage of times these variables had a positive or negative sign for each prediction task. The plot is limited to the 100 most frequently selected variables.

This shows researchers should be careful interpreting prediction models as the identified ‘risk factors’ appear to depend on the design choices. Therefore, we recommend investigating model robustness across settings or using other techniques for ‘risk factor’ detection (e.g. univariate analysis).

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2.9 Explaining patient-level prediction models using feature importance

Feature (or variable) importance is often used to explain prediction models to end-users. These methods rank or measure the predictive power of features. A higher score implies a higher importance of the specific feature, i.e. a larger impact on the model predictions (sensitivity based perspective: “how does the output rely on a variable?”) or model performance (predictive power approach: “how much is the loss function reduced?”). Many methods to compute (global) feature importance exist (1), but clear guidance on which method is best to use is lacking. Permutation feature importance (2, 3) is a popular, straightforward approach that is currently supported in the OHDSI PLP package (4). More recently, Shapley values have been advocated for in the literature (5). In this work, we compare which features are important according to permutation feature importance and Shapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) for a given patient-level prediction model.

We investigated the top 5 ranked features, see Table 6. We found some overlapping features between methods as indicated by the numbers in brackets, e.g. ‘infective corneal ulcer previous 30 days’ and ‘vascular disorder of pelvis previous 30 days’ were included in the top 5 by all methods. However, there are also differences; some features included in the top 5 by one method are ranked much lower by another (e.g. ‘drug use temozolomide previous 365 days’ is on place 13 – 4 – 11 and ‘drug use goserelin previous 30 days’ on place 45 – 27 – 4). In total, 9 different features were identified by the three methods. Note these features should not be interpreted as ‘risk factors’, but only as features that are important for the given prediction model.

The results show some agreement between the methods on the relative importance of features, but also large variation. This is not surprising, given that methods vary in their intended behavior (6). For example, permutation feature importance explains *model performance* and model coefficients/SHAP explain *model predictions*. However, the effect of these differences (i.e. a different feature importance ranking) is not always clear to users of these methods. Knowing which feature importance method is best to use is important for reliable interpretation and presentation of prediction models. This is a first step in that direction and we plan to do a more in-depth analysis of feature importance methods to understand the influence of e.g. correlated features, high dimensionality, and model misspecification.

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Table 6: Top 5 ranked features in the model according to different feature importance methods (in brackets the number of times each feature was included in the top 5).

	Model coefficients	Permutation feature importance	SHAP
1.	Infective corneal ulcer previous 30 days (3x)	Infective corneal ulcer previous 30 days (3x)	Vascular disorder of pelvis previous 30 days (3x)
2.	Vascular disorder of pelvis previous 30 days (3x)	Vascular disorder of pelvis previous 30 days (3x)	Infective corneal ulcer previous 30 days (3x)
3.	Affective psychosis previous 30 days (2x)	Antibiotics and chemotherapeutics for dermatological use at day of visit	Affective psychosis previous 30 days (2x)
4.	Hypertensive disorder previous 30 days	Drug use temozolomide previous 365 days	Drug use goserelin previous 30 days
5.	Neoplasm of intrathoracic organs previous 30 days (2x)	Neoplasm of intrathoracic organs previous 30 days (2x)	Selective calcium channel blockers with direct cardiac effects use previous 365 days

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3. FINAL REMARKS

Over the course of EHDEN project, WP3 has made big strides in both methodological and clinical research into personalized medicine. During the project new methods have been investigated that give context to model performance (Iterative Pairwise External Validation), that demonstrate the use of free text notes in clinical modelling (the TRITON tool), different data manipulation techniques have been examined such as over and under sampling, and frequent pattern mining have been assessed in terms of their added value to the modelling process. The work package has also investigated the role of explainability in the assessment and adoption of models into the clinical process, indeed it was found that the lack of explainability has hindered the adoption of models by clinical partners. This contributed to the methodological research that is still ongoing within the work package into model parsimonisation and showing the value of simple, easily understandable and implementable tools in the field. This work was conducted as part of the COVER Covid-19 response. Further from a clinical perspective, models have been developed for knee replacement surgery, for covid-19, for rheumatoid arthritis and for dementia. Furthermore, a prediction model library has been developed to allow for easy finding and testing of patient-level prediction models. This powerful tool creates a centralized space accessing these prediction models and it is hoped the increased accessibility will lead to more discussion about and indeed implementation of prediction models in clinical practice.

Much progress has been made in the generation of evidence for personalized medicine. The leveraging of the power of the OMOP CDM has allowed dramatic improvements in the understanding of the personal nature of many diseases and the opportunities these present for more tailored treatments. During the remainder of the EHDEN project and beyond, the work group will continue to study methods and will be involved in the application of them in clinical use cases that will be led by the Evidence Generation Taskforce led by WP1 etc. With this work we will be driving the evidence generation and implementation processes and aim to provide real benefit for patients.